

THE RUBRICS

Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies

Volume 7 Issue 4, April 2025

www.therubrics.in

ISSN 2454-1974

Role of Marginalised Women in Bama's Karukku**Sandesh W Sahare***Asst. Professor, Dr. Ambedkar College, Deekshabhoom, Nagpur, India.**sandysahare312@gmail.com*DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15154997>**ABSTRACT**

Bama is a Tamil Dalit writer . She has become a voice of Dalit women through her autobiographical novel. The present research study aimed at marginalised women in Bama's karukku .This study analyses oppressed and depressed women in her novel karakku. This paper argues that Dalit Women faced inequality and gender discrimination and the condition of Dalit women in our Indian society. The term Dalit was first used by Jyotiba Phule in the perspective of oppression faced by the former untouchable in the 19th century. In the present paper, Bama helps us to understand the lives of the Dalits. In the novel karukku Bama presents herself as a Tamil Dalit Christian.

Keywords: Dalit; marginalization; discrimination; oppressed; Christian; autobiography

FULL PAPER

Introduction

In 1958 the term 'Dalit literature' was first used at Dalit conference held in Bombay. Dalit Literature is a post-independence phenomenon. It has a great historical significance. Dalit literature represent collective consciousness of social, political, economic and racial discrimination suffered by the Dalit of hundreds of years. Dalit literature advocates strongly human values such as equality, liberty ,fraternity and justice and accept man's moral attitude. Dalit literature is a literary posture adopted in the movement initiated by Dr. B. R. Ambedkar to remove untouchability. Today Dalit literature is being written in many Indian languages and also translated into many Indian and foreign languages. Dalit literature also written by some Indian languages are Sara Joseph, Kumaran Asan, Mahasweta Devi ,Mulk raj Anand and Premchand. Baburao Bagul, Bandhu Madhav and Shankarrao Kharat gave a new way to Dalit literature. There are some significant writers focuses on Dalit they are; Namdeo Dhasal, Daya Pawar, Arjun Dangle, Baburao Bagul, Perumal Murugan, Urmila Pawar, Omprakash Valmiki, Dr. B. R. Ambedkar, Meena Khandasamy, Kancha Ilaiah, Debi Roy, Raja Dhale, Bhagwan Das and so on.

Bama is a pen name of Bama fausina Soosairaj a Tamil Dalit writer. She has written her first autobiographical novel in 1992 named karukku originally in a dialect of Tamil and it was translated into English by Lakshmi Holmsrom and karukku won the crossword book award in 2000. Karukku describes the life of a Dalit Catholic Christian women. It also show on the caste based oppression in the village untouchability in the catholic convent. The works of Bama present her as a leader of the down-trodden people. She used the word "taazhtapatoor" or "odukkapattor" in Tamil means marginalised or oppressed. The present study focus on marginalization of Dalit women with special reference to Bama's karukku. In 1949 untouchability in any form was legally abolished in India. But today untouchability is seen and experienced as faced by Paraya people in Karukku. Bama was insulted by her headmaster for she belonged to the paraya community. "The elder went straight up to the Naicker bowed low and extended the packet towards him, cupping the hands that held the string with his other hand.....that Naicker's were upper caste and therefore must not touch parayas" (Holmstrom 15) When Bama was a young ,she saw this elder parayas bowing down before a Naicker. Even she didn't know about caste system. The Naicker's, nadars and even the forester are exploited to the

parayas. They are unable to advanced themselves even after working hard because the payment they receive is not appropriate to their labour. Bama is convinced to the Parayas that a social change can happen only with education. (Bama 80) " Who are immersed in ignorance as their capital set up a big business and only profited their own castes". Here Bama describes how church used Dalits. There are many Dalits in churches and the Christian took benefits of the church. Bama makes us realize that there is place for Dalit at churches even Dalit become Priest or Nuns ; they are marginalised by the upper caste Christian. Bama finds new path of renunciation. Roger Mc Namara (p.20) "In the conventional understanding of Christianity ,God is perfect and so cannot accept a world that is sinful. It is Christ Gods son who is also perfect who sacrifices his own life and so beers the burden of the world's sins. Therefore, Christ become the mediator between Gods and humans and it is through belief in him that humans can be forgiven and therefore saved". If all humans are equal before Gods so, how can we define them in class and castes.

"I share the same difficulties and struggle that all Dalits poor experience. I sharethe poverty of the Dalits who toil for more painfully through the fierce heat and beating rain, yet live out their lives in their huts with nothing but gruel and water". (Bama 79) Here Bama is a voice of Dalits and representatives of the Parayas. (Rajkumar 08) Gangadhar Pantawane defines 'Dalits' in a broader way saying, "Dalits believes in humanism. He rejects the existence of God, rebirth soul, sacred books that teach discrimination ,fate and heaven because these have made him a slave. He represent the exploited men...." Gangadhar Pantawane tells us a meaning of Dalits; they believe in karma and humanism and opposed to God existence soul and heaven life. Bama in Karukku also find a new way of life and believes in humanism and rejects God. Karukku describes the sufferings of women in the Dalit community both from young girl to an old woman. Poverty and hunger are the two main problems for Dalits. Still many Dalit women marginalised by the upper castes. Namdeo Dhasal also explained in his poem 'Hunger' the sufferings of Dalits cause of Hunger. For poor people the question of survival becomes more important than anything.

"Most of the Land belong to the Naicker community. Each Naicker's fields were spread over many miles. The fields were spreads....people knew all the fields by their names turned up exactly where they were required to work"(Holmsrom 6) .In the above lines Bama says that Upper caste are not given lands and property to the Dalits to cultivate their own corps. Only living sources are available to the Dalits for survival.

As a child, Bama was raised in an environment deeply rooted in Christian faith. For her, religion was not only about duty and obedience (enforced through strict discipline) but also intertwined with notions of class and caste identity. She quickly becomes aware of her position as a Dalit in Indian society and learns the complexities of being a Dalit within the Catholic Christian community.

Bama focuses on social ,culture and family life of Dalit in karukku. Bama revealed the daily life religion, civilization, celebration, food habits, language culture, entertainment in the Paraya community. She stands for every Dalit women. Bama exposed how the Dalit are exploited and marginalised by the upper caste based system. Dalits are exploited everywhere like schools, colleges, market, buses. Here author tells us that in her school she was called a 'Thief' because of her community. Bama says: "You climbed the coconut tree yesterday after everybody else had gone home and you stole a coconut. We cannot allow you inside this school."(karukku 16) In Karukku Bama is not against caste oppression but as a Dalit woman who wants equality and justice. In Karukku Bama focuses on helpless lives and marginalised women of the Dalits. Caste and Gender are two important Facets for the study of Dalit Feminism. Dalit feminism reconstructs the definition of Women marginalization and oppression. Dalit Women suffered and harass in two aspect first ; being a woman and being a Dalit. Hence, they are double marginalised. She recounts how, on public buses, people frequently asked her about her place of residence, and when she disclosed her street name, which revealed her caste, she was told to vacate her seat after the person sitting next to her. When she resisted, the other person would often stand up but never sit next to her again. Her mother often suggested that she should lie about her caste, believing it would go unnoticed, but Bama refused to do so. For Bama, it was a form of resistance, a protest against the systemic injustice her community faced.

The story unfolds with a raw depiction of the untouchability, social exclusion, and economic inequality faced by Dalits. Bama courageously highlights the contradictions within the Church, which, despite being an institution that claims to represent equality, continues to uphold caste-based divisions. Bama's narrative is a tale of her disillusionment with the promise of freedom and dignity that comes with being an Indian. A central part of her story is the sense of betrayal she experienced in the convent and the Church. Karukku recounts her childhood journey as a Catholic and her eventual realization of her Dalit identity. Even within her spiritual life, religious festivals, tied to the cycles of crops and seasons, shaped her experiences.

Later, she explores the religious and social systems that kept Dalits confined to their untouchable status. Throughout her life, Bama endured harsh experiences, and her feelings and reflections on Karukku are revealed in the preface of the book. In India Dalit women are exploited and marginalized on the basis of cast based system, gender, class, and caste. There are many Dalit and other Writers have been writing on Dalit women ,feminism, tribal problems ,oppressed and depressed class as we see in writings of Bama and Meena Khandasamy. According to Bama the word Dalit refers to oppressed and exploited people belongs to lower caste in India. The autobiography karukku is a panorama of downtrodden people and life story of Bama. Vellaiyamma is grandmother of Bama plays an important role in her village as a midwife . She brings up her two daughters singlehandedly. Her husband Goyindan left her wife after four years of marriage. Bama gets inspiration from her grandmother. 'Periamma' aunt of Bama is like a child bearing machine. She works the whole in the fields and home but at night she surrenders her to satisfy her husband sexually. One day she refused to fulfill his sexual gratification. She was killed by her husband Samudrakani. On the other hand he has no apologize for his wife's death. Vellaiyamma and Periamma are marginalised in their society . This autobiography highlights the way low-caste individuals are treated as untouchables due to societal caste biases. Those from lower castes not only show respect towards higher-caste individuals but are also seen as contaminating everything they come into contact with. The upper-caste people in Bama's village avoid Cheri, where she lives, because all the essential services, such as the post office, panchayat, board, mill, temple, large shop, church, and school, are located in their own part of the Village. A Dalit woman's life is filled with constant challenges. Bama expresses regret for being born a female, blaming herself for her circumstances. She also criticizes the Government for failing to provide her with a job, despite her qualifications. In Bama's view, both married and unmarried Dalit women are often disrespected by society.

Conclusion

Dalit women still suffer from many ways. Today there are many Constitutional rules made for their rights. But in our Society the exploitation and marginalization of Dalit Women is still common. Dalit women faced domestic violence, gender discrimination and domination both inside and outside of their house. The present study focuses on double oppression by the double patriarchies on Dalit women. Marginalization of women and their status in Indian society clearly visible in the writings of Dalit writers. Bama

tells us a message to all Dalit women; education is the only way can change their life.

Works cited

Bama, Karukku: Translated Lakshmi Holmstrom, New Delhi OUP, Second Edition.

Roger Mc Namara. 'Rational Thought and the Dalitization of Christianity in Karukku' South Asian Review 30:1. 2009

Rajkumar: 'Dalit Literature and Criticism' University of Delhi Orient Black Swan Publication (first edition 2019)

Bama, Karukku: Translated Lakshmi Holmstrom, Macmillan India limited, Chennai-2000. Print.